

SOME HIGH STRAIN RATE EFFECTS ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Data from high strain rate experiments performed on the University of Delaware Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar are analyzed and systematically compared. These compressive data include strength to failure, strain to failure, strain energy to failure and elastic modulus. The strain rates involved vary from "static" values up to 2000 sec.^{-1} . While most of the data presented are at 21°C (70°F), some -151°C (-240°F), 93°C (200°F), 120°C (250°F) and 204°C (400°F) data are also presented.

Polymer matrix composites tested include unidirectional E-glass/epoxy, random nonwoven glass/polyester, unidirectional T40/ERL 1908 graphite/epoxy, unidirectional AS4/3501 graphite/epoxy, quasi-isotropic AS4 cloth/3501 graphite epoxy, and Metton (a thermosetting reaction injection molded plastic). 6061-T6 aluminum as well as carbon/aluminum and silicon carbide reinforced aluminum metal matrix composites have been tested. In ceramic matrix composites, carbon/glass unidirectional continuous fiber results as well as a discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced glass matrix material have also been treated. Meaningful statistical analyses have been made of data for the graphite epoxy, the E-glass epoxy, Al/SiC, and the glass/polyester and are reported on herein.

By analyzing the data from these several research efforts using the same statistical analyses and uniform data presentation, the maximum information is gleaned. In all cases strain rate effects are significant and cannot be ignored in design and analysis for structures operating in a dynamic environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Material systems are usually characterized by their mechanical properties such as modulus of elasticity, yield strength and ultimate strength. Testing to determine these properties is normally performed in accordance with the American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards, which are typically at low or quasi-static strain rates (less than .01/sec). These properties are almost always used by designers in analyzing structures subjected to dynamic and shock environments which differ from the ASTM static conditions.

There has been much research published which shows that for many metals the mechanical properties vary significantly with strain rate (e.g., [1]). Various theories have been proposed to

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account for these effects. These theories include dislocation substructures [2], thermally activated mechanisms [3] and internal variables [4]. There has been less research published on the subject of high strain rate testing of composite materials. However, the limited data available indicates that composite materials also have properties which vary significantly with strain rate.

The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) is widely used to conduct high strain rate tension, compression or torsion tests. The SHPB compression tests associated with this investigation consist of impacting a short cylindrical specimen between two long steel bars. The strain rates range from 100 to 2000/sec.

For the composite material systems involved in this investigation there were little or no high strain rate test data available. The data was gathered during the research of Finch, Choe, and Frey [5, 6, 7] for their Master's thesis. Later papers were published regarding this research by Choe, Finch and Vinson [8], Frey, Vinson and Hall [9], and Frey, Vinson and Prewo [10]. These investigations provide new insight into the composite material behavior under high strain rate loading conditions and should be useful in the analysis of structures using these materials. This is important especially with the increasing use of composite materials. The material systems tested include aluminum, E-glass/epoxy glass/polyester, graphite/epoxy Metton, carbon/glass, carbon/aluminum, and Silicon Carbide reinforced aluminum.

The SHPB equipment is shown in Figure 1, [6]. Impact is initiated by releasing nitrogen gas from a pressurized chamber which causes the specimen to be impacted between the two bars. The striker bar is displaced on Teflon rings through the barrel where it strikes the incident bar (bar 1). The velocity of the striker bar V_{SB} just prior to impact is measured using two infrared beams set four inches apart.

Upon impact with the striker bar, the incident bar receives an elastic compressive strain wave with a wave velocity C_B and a wave shape $\epsilon_I(t)$ and is displaced along its length axis. This bar is guided by Teflon bearings which are bolted to a steel I beam and secured on a reinforced concrete base to minimize any vibration. When the wave reaches the bar 1-specimen interface, a portion of the incident wave is reflected back into bar 1 as a tensile wave with a wave shape $\epsilon_R(t)$. The remaining portion is transmitted into the specimen as a compressive wave. The wave transmitted into the specimen travels through the specimen and reaches the specimen-bar 2 interface, where a portion of the wave is reflected back into the specimen as a tensile wave. The remaining portion is transmitted into bar 2 as a compressive wave with a wave shape $\epsilon_T(t)$. This bar is displaced similarly to bar 1 but is caught after the test by a simple dashpot.

Because the specimen length is short compared to the bar lengths, the initial stress wave in the specimen undergoes numerous internal reflections during the test. It is calculated that the initial wave duration in a typical specimen is approximately two microseconds. Within a composite material specimen, there may be differences in the speed of the wave in the fiber and matrix materials. For clarity, these specimen internal reflections are not shown in the Lagrangian diagram of the SHPB equipment shown in Figure 2 taken from [11]. Due to the numerous reflections, the stress distribution along the specimen length is smoothed out and the specimen is assumed to be in a uniform state of stress at any instant [12]. The Lagrangian diagram shows that there is a characteristic time window corresponding to the duration of the wave pulses. This is defined as the time it takes a wave to travel the length of the striker bar and back. For the University of Delaware SHPB, the wave pulse time window is approximately 290 microseconds. Thus, to record information accurately at specimen failure, the specimen must fail within 290 microseconds after the start of the test.

Strain gages are mounted on bars 1 and 2 equidistant from the specimen interfaces and are connected to the oscilloscope. A third strain gage, mounted on bar 1 near the striker bar, acts as a trigger for the oscilloscope. The oscilloscope records the strain gauges output as voltage versus time curves. A disk drive is connected directly to the oscilloscope and can store the data on a floppy disk. Using this data, the stress and strain versus time of the specimen during the test can

be calculated, for the strain rate of that particular test.

2. DATA ANALYSIS

The data generated during each test are the two voltage versus time curves and the time taken by the striker bar to cross the two infrared beams. Measurements of each specimen's length and diameter must be recorded prior to the test. The details of analyzing the voltage versus time curves and a discussion of the computational equations and their use are given by Frey, Vinson and Hall [9] and Frey [7].

3. PRESENT STUDY

In studying the data generated using the same SHPB and its instrumentation, it became clear that a systematic statistical analyses of the data may prove fruitful in quantifying certain trends and comparisons among various materials. In addition, through this statistical analysis there is a possibility, through the increased lucidity, that more insight may be obtained toward developing a more fundamental understanding of the behavior and failure of the materials as functions of strain rate and temperature.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

An analysis of the data regarding a unidirectional E-Glass/3501 epoxy ($V_f = 60\%$) is shown in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curves of this material in the fiber direction for a variety of strain rates and temperatures. The equations associated with Figure 3 are as follows:

◆ Room Temperature, Strain Rate= 250	$y = 1.4535 + 3.2188e+4x - 2.9934e+5x^2$ $R^2 = 0.997$
✕ Room Temperature, Strain Rate=400	$y = 1.0654 + 3.5363e+4x - 3.5620e+5x^2$ $R^2 = 0.995$
◆ Room Temperature, Strain Rate =600	$y = 0.94260 + 5.0898e+4x - 7.1952e+5x^2$ $R^2 = 0.997$
■ -151 C, Strain Rate = 400 (1/sec)	$y = 13.603 + 3.4362e+4x - 3.5199e+5x^2$ $R^2 = 0.996$
□ 93 C, Strain Rate = 400 (1/sec)	$y = 13.603 + 3.4362e+4x - 3.5199e+5x^2$ $R^2 = 0.996$
▲ 204 C, Strain Rate = 400 (1/sec)	$y = -7.8901 + 4.5153e+4x - 6.9356e+5x^2$ $R^2 = 0.997$

The first thing to notice is the very high correlation values of each equation, i.e. all above 0.99. (regression is based on least squares) It is interesting that through the statistical analysis a second order polynomial is sufficient to attain the high correlation. Also for the curves it is seen that at most the ordinate value (i.e. strain = 0) is less than 14 MPa, which is less than 1.6% of the ultimate strength - a nice curve fit. It is also seen that the curves representing room temperature, $\dot{\epsilon} = 250s^{-1}$, and the curves representing $\dot{\epsilon} = 400s^{-1}$ at room temperature, $-151^\circ C$ ($-240^\circ F$) and $+93^\circ C$ ($+200^\circ F$) all lie roughly along the same curve. So for a strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 400s^{-1}$, temperature has little effect on this material between $-151^\circ C \leq T \leq +93^\circ C$. ($-240^\circ F \leq T \leq +200^\circ F$)

However, for this material a different behavior is noticed at room temperature when the strain rate reaches $\dot{\epsilon} = 600s^{-1}$. At this strain rate the modulus of elasticity is higher, the ultimate strength is higher, and the curve peaks and recedes - a far different material behavior than at lower strain rates. This implies that the mechanism governing elastic stiffness has changed from the lower strain rates.

Similarly at $\dot{\epsilon} = 400s^{-1}$, for a temperature of $204^\circ C$ ($400^\circ F$) a behavior significantly differing from that of the material at lower temperatures is observed.

It is seen that for this E-glass/epoxy composite, the behavior begins to vary significantly

somewhere between strain rates of $\dot{\epsilon} = 400s^{-1}$ and $\dot{\epsilon} = 600s^{-1}$, as well as for temperature somewhere between 93°C (200°F) and 204°C (400°F). The latter effect is quite understandable qualitatively, but the quantitative results are seen only by this type of detailed analysis.

Figure 4 is a plot of ultimate strength as a function of strain rate for the E-glass epoxy composite. In each case it is seen that there is a significant increase in strength as a function of strain rate. The correlation is acceptable for both room temperature and -151°C (-240°F) but it is not acceptable for the 93°C (250°F) data, which is included here only for illustration. Obviously, more data is needed at 93°C. It is also seen that the behavior of the material differs significantly between -151°C and room temperature.

Data for the unidirectional AS4-3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite ($V_f = 60\%$) in the fiber direction is shown in Figure 5, where the equations for each curve are given by:

◆ Room Temperature, Strain Rate= 250	$y = -2.8675 + 4.7892e+4x - 7.6993e+5x^2$	$R^2 = 0.995$
✕ Room Temperature, Strain Rate=400	$y = -0.41507 + 4.8145e+4x - 6.9799e+5x^2$	$R^2 = 0.990$
◆ Room Temperature, Strain Rate =600	$y = -1.3334e-2 + 5.1387e+4x - 7.3581e+5x^2$	$R^2 = 0.991$
■ -151 C, Strain Rate = 400 (1/sec)	$y = -8.5748 + 5.2790e+4x - 7.5582e+5x^2$	$R^2 = 0.996$
□ 93 C, Strain Rate = 400 (1/sec)	$y = -5.4097 + 5.2683e+4x - 7.8778e+5x^2$	$R^2 = 0.998$
▲ 204 C, Strain Rate = 400 (1/sec)	$y = -9.3915 + 6.6497e+4x - 1.5274e+6x^2$	$R^2 = 0.996$

The stress-strain curves again show a very good statistical correlation (>0.99). It's again interesting to see that the statistical curves all meet at the ordinate with values less than 9.39 MPa (absolute) which is at most 1% of the stress at 3% strain.

It is seen that for this graphite epoxy the curves all behave similarly except for the tests at 204°C (400°F), where one would expect the composite with an epoxy matrix to behave differently - but would not be able to predict how differently except through the statistical analysis of the tests.

If one looks at the second term of the statistical fit, one can say this is a modulus parameter. For the three room temperature curves, one sees that the modulus increases monotonically with increasing strain rates, with a 7.3% increase between $\dot{\epsilon} = 250s^{-1}$ and $\dot{\epsilon} = 600s^{-1}$. At $\dot{\epsilon} = 400s^{-1}$, over a range of temperatures, no conclusions can be made regarding modulus as a function of temperature.

Figure 6 is a plot of ultimate strength as a function of strain ratio for a [0°/90°] plain weave E-glass/Cycom 4102 polyester matrix composite ($V_f = 51.2\%$). First the correlation is not good, and the shape of the curve certainly suggests anomalies in behavior. Obviously more data needs to be obtained. The equation for this curve is given as

$$y = 12.656 + 1.3882x - 1.2966e-3x^2 + 4.6066e-7x^3 \quad R^2 = 0.682$$

Looking now at the plot of strain to failure as a function of strain rate for the glass polyester in Figure 7 one can surmise that there definitely is a change in failure mechanism somewhere around the strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 750s^{-1}$. Obviously this needs further study.

Lastly Figure 8 shows a plot of the stress strain curve of silicon carbide reinforced aluminum ($V_f = 15\%$) at a strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 400s^{-1}$, and room temperature. Only limited data is available, and the equation for this curve is given as

$$y = 14.407 + 3.0742e+4x - 6.0530e+5x^2 + 3.7015e+6x^3 \quad R^2 = 0.881$$

It is seen that the correlation is marginal - more data is needed. The curve as a result has a strange turn-up near 8% strain. Even so the ordinate value is less than 3% of the ultimate stress.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A few examples have been given of the behaviors of various composites at high strain rates. One can conclude that:

- a. strain rate effects are significant in general for all composite materials, or at least one should assume so until proven otherwise by numerous tests, and subsequent analysis
- b. far more high strain rate testing should be done for these and other composites of interest over a variety of temperatures
- c. testing various materials, and statistically analyzing the data provides unique insight into the material behavior necessary and desirable to subsequently develop theories of behavior and failure or fracture.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 2.1: University of Delaware SHPB Equipment

Figure 2.2: Lagrangian Diagram for the University of Delaware SHPB Equipment

Stress vs Strain For E Glass/Epoxy

Figure 3

Stress vs Strain Rate for E Glass/Epoxy

Figure 4

Stress vs Strain for Graphite Epoxy

Figure 5

Ultimate Stress vs Strain Rate for Glass/Polyester

Figure 6

Ultimate Strain vs Strain Rate for Glass/Polyester

Figure 7

Stress vs Strain for Al/Sic

Figure 8